

Assessment of Pollution Characteristics of Selected Toxic Heavy Metals in Soil from Industrial, Urban and Rural Areas in Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria

*¹Nwoye, E.E., ²Salami, S.J., ²Gongden, J.J.

¹Department of Chemistry, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano state, Nigeria

²Department of Chemistry, University of Jos, Plateau state, Nigeria

Abstract-: *The soil is becoming increasingly polluted with chemicals and other toxic heavy metal pollutants which can reach the food chain and can be ultimately ingested by man. Heavy metals find their entry into the soil and accumulate in toxic concentrations becoming sources of pollution to the environment. The harmful effects of heavy metals are linked to accumulation in biological system even in their lowest form of development. Heavy metals can end up in soil from various sources and the greatest concern is the application of soil sludge/inorganic manure to agricultural soil. Under appropriate conditions the metals could be absorbed by the plant roots either causing direct injury to plants or being accumulated and passing into the food chain. Heavy metal concentrations in soil exert a decisive impact on soil quality and its use in food production particularly in an industrial area. Heavy metal toxicity can lead to cancer, damage or reduced mental and central nervous function, lower energy levels and damage to blood composition, lungs, kidneys, liver, and other vital organs. This study assesses the concentration and pollution characteristics of selected toxic heavy metals in the soil from industrial, urban and rural areas using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS).*

Keywords: Heavy metals, soil, pollution characteristics, toxic pollutants, AAS.

Email: elsnowelo@yahoo.com

Received: July 16, 2023

Revised: August 30, 2023

Accepted: September 18, 2023

About the Journal: SJANS is a multidisciplinary science journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Science, Nigeria Police Academy, Kano, Nigeria

1.0 Introduction

Soil is a very important natural resources that plays a vital role in sustaining basic human needs. It is a vital resource of sustaining basic human needs, a quality food, food supply and a live able environment without soil the earth would be as barren as the moon hence lifeless (Manta *et al.*, 2002). According to Khan *et al* 1994, soil can act as either a sink or source. Soils are the major sink for heavy metals released into the environment by aforementioned anthropogenic activities and unlike organic contaminants which are oxidized to carbon (IV) oxide by microbial action, most metals do not undergo microbial or chemical degradation, and their total concentration in soils persists for a long time after their introduction (Khan *et al.*, 1994).

There are myriads of pollution, such as soil pollution, affecting living organisms, which include the plants. Soil is often contaminated by human activities and this is reflected in the high horizontal and vertical variability brought about by the anthropogenic influence on soil formation and development (Fong *et al.*, 2008). A variety of human activities including municipal waste

disposal, industrial emissions, military testing and agricultural practices have left their impacts on soils in the form of elevated and high level of toxicants (Vouta *et al.*, 1996). Heavy metals find their entry into the soil and accumulate in toxic concentrations becoming sources of pollution in the soil. The concentration of heavy metals in soil and their impact on ecosystems can be influenced by many factors such as the parent rock, climate and anthropogenic activities (Fong *et al.*, 2008). Among the pollutants that persist and accumulate in the soils include; inorganic toxic compounds for example fertilizers, organic wastes, organic pesticides and radionuclides (Jaradat and Momami 1999).The soil is thus becoming increasingly polluted with chemicals and other heavy metal pollutants which can reach the food chain and can be ultimately ingested by man (Nwoye, 2022).

Chemical features of soils are dependent on the kind of weathered rocks in study areas leading to contamination of both soil and plants. Despite its importance, soil is often contaminated by human activities and this is reflected in the high horizontal and vertical variability brought about by the anthropogenic influence on soil formation and development (Fong *et al.*, 2008). A variety of human activities

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

including municipal waste disposal, industrial emissions, military testing and agricultural practices have left their impacts on soils in the form of elevated and high level of toxicants (Vouta et al., 1996).

Heavy metals occur naturally in the soil environment from the pedogenetic processes of weathering of parent materials at levels that are regarded as trace (<1000 mg kg⁻¹) and rarely toxic (Kabata-Pendias., 2001). Heavy metals occur naturally in the ecosystem with large variations in concentration (Sholadoye and Nwoye, 2015). Due to the disturbance and acceleration of nature’s slowly occurring geochemical cycle of metals by man, most soils of industrial and urban environments may accumulate one or more of the heavy metals above defined background values high enough to cause risks to human health, plants, animals, ecosystems, or other media. It is projected that the anthropogenic emission into the atmosphere, for several heavy metals, is one-to-three orders of magnitude higher than natural fluxes. Metal-bearing solids at contaminated sites can originate from a wide variety of anthropogenic sources in the form of metal mine tailings, disposal of high metal wastes in improperly protected landfills, leaded gasoline and lead based paints, land application of fertilizer, animal manures, biosolids (sewage sludge), compost, pesticides, coal combustion residues, petrochemicals, and atmospheric deposition (Khan et al., 1994). Heavy metals are probably the most harmful and insidious contaminants, due to their biological non-biodegradable nature and their potential to cause adverse effects at certain level of exposure and absorption (Demirozu et al., 2002). Toxic heavy metals concentrations in soil exert a decisive impact on soil quality and its use in food production particularly in an industrial area.

Heavy metals enter the human body mainly through two routes which are inhalation and ingestion. Ingestion is the main route of exposure to these elements in human population (Sawick et al., 2021). Absorption through the skin is another route of exposure when the metals come in contact with humans in agriculture and in manufacturing, pharmaceutical, industrial, or residential settings. Industrial exposure accounts for a common route of exposure for adults (Kacholi and Sahu, 2018). Ingestion is the most common route of exposure in children. Children may acquire toxic levels from the normal hand-to-mouth activity with contaminated soil or by actually eating objects

that are not food (Dupler, 2001). Chronic accumulation of heavy metals in the kidney and liver of humans causes disruption of numerous biochemical processes, leading to cardiovascular, nervous, kidney and bone diseases. Furthermore, the consumption of heavy metal-contaminated food can seriously deplete some essential nutrients in the body causing a decrease in immunological defenses, intrauterine growth retardation, impaired psycho- social behavior, disabilities associated with malnutrition and a high prevalence of upper gastrointestinal cancer (Jarup, 2003).

2.0 Material and Method

10.0g each of the air-dried fine soil sample was weighed and transferred into an acid washed beaker. 10cm³ concentrated trioxonitrate(v) acid (HNO₃) was added and the mixture heated gently for 1 hour on a thermostat hot plate at a temperature of 120°C. The solid residues were digested further with 5 ml 3:1 concentrated H₂SO₄ and HCl mixture at 120°C for 10 minutes. Further heating on a hot plate sporadically was carried to assure a fixed temperature of 150°C for 5 hours until the acid fumes were finally evaporated (Ogunwale et al., 2021). The mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature. 50ml of distilled water was added, stirred and filtered into 100 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with distilled water. All analyses were run in triplicates. The digested samples were subjected to Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Model number; Perkin Elmer PinAAcle 900H) for total metal concentration in the Soil samples.

4.0 Results and Discussion

Table 1: Mean Concentrations (mg/kg) of heavy metals in soil samples from different areas

Sample Area	MetalConcentration(mg/kg)			
	Cd	Cr	Ni	Pb
Industrial	0.02±0.01	3.23±1.938	0.75±0.13	9.95±4.21
Urban	0.04±0.02	0.97±0.46	0.91±0.27	6.92±2.73
Rural	0.01±0.00	0.93±0.68	0.57±0.214	7.27±3.28
WHO permissible limit	0.8	100	35	50

Figure 1: Concentration of cadmium in the soil samples

The concentration of Cadmium ranges from 0.01-0.03mg/kg in industrial area, 0.01-0.06 mg/kg in urban area and 0.01-0.02 mg/kg in rural area respectively as shown in fig. 13. The concentration of Cadmium in the soil samples are in the order urban area > industrial area > rural area with the mean and standard deviation of 0.04 ± 0.02 mg/kg, 0.02 ± 0.01 mg/kg and 0.01 ± 0.00 mg/kg respectively. Cd concentration may be attributed to disposal of condemned automobile parts and car tyre. Cadmium as additives present in lubricating oil as well as about 20-90µg/g of Cd has reported in car tyres as contamination during vulcanization process (Jaradat and Momani, 1999).

The target organs of cadmium toxicity have been identified as liver, placenta, kidneys, lungs, brain and bones (Sobha *et al.*, 2007). Depending on the severity of exposure, the symptoms of effects include nausea, vomiting abdominal cramps, dyspnea and muscular weakness. Severe exposure may result in pulmonary odema and death. Pulmonary effects (emphysema, bronchiolitis and alveolitis) and renal effects may occur following sub chronic inhalation exposure to cadmium and its compounds (Suruibe *et al.*, 2007).

Figure 2: Concentration of chromium in the soil samples

The concentration of chromium ranges from 0.84-6.50mg/kg in industrial area, 0.48-1.78mg/kg in urban area and 0.23-1.62mg/kg in

rural area respectively as shown in fig. 16. The concentration of chromium in the soil samples are in the order industrial area > urban area > rural area with the mean and standard deviation of 3.23 ± 1.94 mg/kg, 0.97 ± 0.46 mg/kg and 0.93 ± 0.68 mg/kg respectively.

Cr occurs naturally in rocks, through mining and industrial activities, disposal of hospital waste and waste incineration. Cr is released into the environment contaminating sources of air, water and soil. Numerous vitro studies have indicated that excessive Cr^{3+} in the cell can cause DNA damage (Adeleken and Abegunde, 2011). Also, the carcinogenicity of chromate dust is known for a long time, and in 1890 the first publication described the elevated cancer risk of workers in a chromate dye company (Newman, 2001; Langard, 2005).

Figure 3: Concentration of nickel in the soil samples

The concentration of nickel ranges from 0.64 - 0.81mg/kg in industrial area, 0.54-1.38mg/kg in urban area and 0.25-0.88mg/kg in rural area respectively as shown in fig. 19. The concentration of nickel in the soil samples are in the order urban area > industrial area > rural area with the mean and standard deviation of 0.91 ± 0.27 mg/kg, 0.75 ± 0.13 mg/kg, 0.57 ± 0.21 mg/kg, respectively.

The high concentration of nickel in the urban area can be attributed to smoke emission from automobile exhaust of vehicles, cigarette smoke, manufacturing emissions and airborne waste. (WHO, 1996). Radziemska *et al.* (2013) studied the heavy metals contaminated Soil, natural environment contamination highly with nickel the highest increase was shown by soil contamination with amount of $240 \text{ mg Ni kg}^{-1}$. Mohammed *et al.* (2012) investigated that amount of nickel differ in soil samples which were collected from different sites with distribution of residual, oxides of Fe and Mn

oxide and carbonate (organically bound phases). The results indicated that concentration of nickel was higher than tolerance limit of 50 mg/kg in few sampling locations. The nickel concentration in this research is within the WHO permissible limit.

Figure 4: Concentration of lead in the soil samples

The concentration of lead ranges from 0.60 - 1.31mg/kg in industrial area, 0.42-0.95 mg/kg in urban area and 0.47-1.59 mg/kg in rural area respectively as shown in fig. 20. The concentration of lead in the soil samples are in the order urban area > industrial area > rural area with the mean and standard deviation of 0.91±0.39 mg/kg, 0.77±0.25 mg/kg and 0.58±0.18 mg/kg respectively.

The use of lead in batteries, bearing metals, cable covering, gasoline additives, explosives and ammunition as well as in manufacture of pesticides, antifouling paints and analytical reagents has caused widespread environmental contamination. Lead can also be emitted from industrial plants, metal smelting and battery waste (USEPA, 2018).

The critical and most sensitive effect of Pb is in infants and involves the nervous system. It impairs neurodevelopment, interferes with neurotransmitter function, and disrupts calcium metabolism (ATSDR, 2007). Lead has been shown to be associated with impaired neurobehavioral functioning in children and has been considered to be the most critical effect (Codex, 2011). Pb can cause renal toxicity, developmental delays, hypertension, anaemia, memory loss, anorexia, and brain damage (Malik and Khan, 2016; Madilonga et al., 2020) **Geo-Accumulation Index**

Geo-Accumulation Index represents a quantitative measurement of metal pollution in an environment (Asaah and Abimbola, 2005). Index of Geo-accumulation (Igeo) has been used widely to evaluate the degree of metal pollution in terrestrial, aquatic and marine environment. The Igeo of a metal in a sample was calculated using equation one (Asaah and Abimbola, 2005).

$$I_{geo} = \log_2 \left[\frac{C_n}{1.5 B_n} \right] \quad (1)$$

Where C_n is the concentration of the heavy metal in the sample and B_n is the concentration of the metal in the unpolluted sample. The correction factors 1.5, was used to minimize the effect of the possible variation in the background values which may be attributed to lithogenic variations in the sample. The degree of metal pollution is assessed in terms of

$I_{geo} \leq 0$ Practically unpolluted,
 $1 < I_{geo} \leq 1$ Unpolluted to moderately polluted,
 $2 < I_{geo} \leq 3$ Moderately polluted,
 $3 < I_{geo} \leq 4$ Strongly polluted, $4 < I_{geo} \leq 5$ Strongly to very strongly polluted,
 $5 < I_{geo} \leq 6$ Very strongly polluted, (VSP). (Oyekunle et al., 2011)

Table 2: Geo-accumulation index (Igeo) mg/kg of soil samples in three different areas

Heavy metal(mg/kg)	Industrial area	Urban area	Rural area
Cd	0.68	0.91	0.98
Cr	5.19	0.07	0.07
Ni	1.25	0.43	1.01
Pb	0.67	0.19	0.61

The Geo-accumulation index for industrial area as shown from table 2 indicates that Cd, Ni, and Pb are unpolluted to moderately polluted. Cr in the industrial area is very strongly polluted. In the urban area, Cd is unpolluted to moderately polluted. Cr, Ni and Pb are practically unpolluted.

In the rural area, Cd, Ni and Pb are unpolluted to moderately polluted while Cr is practically unpolluted.

The pollution of chromium in the industrial area can be attributed to industrial activities, disposal of hospital waste and waste incineration. Among the health effects brought about by the exposure to chromium VI include lung cancer, malignant neoplasia, chromium dermatitis and skin ulcers (Smith and Cook, 1996).

Conclusion

Toxic heavy metal pollutants are major source of concern to environmentalist. Their impact on the soil and at large the environment are quite enormous. The pollution of chromium in the industrial area pose great health risk to the entire populace which is attributed to industrial

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

activities, disposal of hospital waste and waste incineration.

The concentrations of the toxic heavy metals in the industrial, urban, and rural areas are in the order (Pb>Cr>Ni>Cd). None of these toxic heavy metals is above the WHO permissible limits. **Acknowledgement**

The authors' profound gratitude goes to the Director and Division's personnel of Bayero University Central Laboratory, Kano, for their unalloyed support and encouragement during this research work.

References

Asaah, V.A., Abimbola, A.F., & Such, C.E.

(2005). Heavy metal concentrations and distribution in surface soil of the Bassa Industrial Zone 1, Douala, Cameroon. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 31 (2.A): 142 – 158.

Agencies for Toxic Substances Death Registry, ATSDR (2007). Toxicological profile for lead. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry, pg. 35-151.

Codex Alimentarius Commission (CAC). (2011). Evaluation of certain food additives and contaminants. FAO/WHO, 2001, Codex stan. 230 - 2001, Rev. 1-2003, Rome.

Demirozu, B., & Saldamli, I. (2002). Metallic contamination problem in a pasta production plant. *Turkish J. Eng. Environ. Sci.*, 26: 361-5.

Dupler, D. (2001). Heavy metals poisoning. *Gale encyclopedia of alternative medicine*. Farmington Hills. Pp. 23-26.

Jaradat, Q.M., & Momami, K.A. (1999). Contamination of roadside soils, plants and air with

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

heavy metals in Jordan : A Comparative study. *Turkish Journal of chemistry*, 23:209-220.

Jarup, L. (2003). "Hazards of heavy metal contamination," *British Medical Bulletin*, vol. 68, pp. 167–182.

Kabata-Pendias, A., & Pendias, H. (2001). Trace metals in soils and plants, CRC Press, Boca Raton, Fla, USA, 2nd edition. pp. 149–153.

Kacholi, D.S., & Sahu, M. (2018). Levels and health Risk assessment of heavy metals in soil, water, and vegetables of dares salaam, *Tanzania. J. Chem.* 1402674.

Khan, A, M., Ibrahim, N., Ahmad, A., & Anwar, S.A.

(1994). Accumulation of heavy metals in soil receiving sewage effluent. *J. Agric. Res.* 32: 525-533.

Madilonga, R.T., Edokpayi, J.N., Volenzo, E.T., Durowoju, O.S., & Odiyo, J.O. (2021). Water quality assessment and evaluation of human health risk in Mutangwi river, Limpopo Province, South Africa. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18: 6765.

Manta, D. S., Angelone, M., Bellanca, A., Neri, R., Sprovieri, M. (2002). Heavy metal in urban soils: a case study from the city of Perlemo (Sicily), Italy. *Sci. Total Environ.* 300: 229-243

McBride, M.B. (2003). Toxic metal in sewage sludge-amended soil: has promotion of beneficial use discounted the risk. *Journal of Advance in Environmental Research*, 8:5-19.

Malik, Q.A., Khan, M.S. (2016). Effect on human

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

- health due to drinking water contaminated with heavy metals. *Journal of Pollution Effects and Control*, 5: 179.
- Mohammed, S.S., Abdulmalik, I.A., Abdulkadir, F.M. (2013). Investigation of chemical fraction of nickel in maize and soil using the cold extraction technique. *Adv. J Food Sci. Tech.* 5(2):137-143.
- Nwoye, E. E., & Thaddeus, O. O. (2019). Determination of some selected heavy metals in carrot and cabbage samples in Wudil, Kano State. *YUMSCIC Journal of Science*.vol.4. Pg. 169-172.
- Oyekunle, J.A., Oluyemi, E.A., Feuyit, G., & Oguntowokan, A.O. (2011). Heavy metal concentrations in soils, leaves and crops grown around dump sites in Lafia Metropolis, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 2(5): 89-96.
- Radziemska, M., & Mazur, Z. (2005). Effect of compost from by-product of the fishing industry on crop yield and microelement content in maize. *J Ecol. Eng.* 16(4):168–175.
- Sawicka, E., Jurkowska, K., & Piwowar, A. (2021). Chromium (III) and chromium (VI) as important players in the induction of genotoxicity – current view. *Annals of Agricultural and Environmental Medicine*, 28(1): 1–10.
- Sholadoye, Q. O., & Nwoye, E.E. (2015). Heavy metal assessment of dumpsite soil in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. *Asian Journal of Science and Technology* Vol.06, Issue, 11, pp.2006-2009.
- Smith, C.J., Hopmans, P., & Cook, F.J. (1996). Accumulation of Cr, Pb, Cu, Ni and Cd in soil following irrigation with untreated effluents in Australia. *Environ Pollut.*, 94: 317- 323.
- United State Environmental Protection Agency, USEPA (1999). Determination of metals in ambient particulate matter using inductively coupled plasma/mass spectrometry (ICP/MS). Centre for Environmental Research Information, Office of Research and Development, US Environmental Protection Agency, Cincinnati, OH, EPA/625/R-96/010a.
- Vouta, D., Grianins, A., & Samara, C. (1996). Trace element in vegetable grown in an industrial area in relation to soil and air particulate World Health Organization/Food and Agricultural Organization, WHO/FAO (1996). Trace Elements in Human Nutrition and health. World Health Organisation, Geneva . Switzerland, pp. 189.
- matter. *Environ Pollut.*, 94:325-333.